

Spatial and Temporal Analysis of Agricultural Land Use in Ambedkar Nagar District, Uttar Pradesh (1999–2023)

Paper Id : 20913 Submission Date : 2025-11-11 Acceptance Date : 2025-11-21 Publication Date : 2025-11-25

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.18093685

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Abstract

This paper investigates the evolving patterns of agricultural land use in Ambedkar Nagar district, situated in the eastern plains of Uttar Pradesh, over the period 1999 to 2023. The analysis is primarily based on secondary sources, supported by field observations and informal farmer interactions. Findings reveal that while the rice–wheat system continues to dominate, significant shifts have occurred in cropping practices. These include a steady contraction of coarse cereals and several pulses, a rapid expansion of cash crops such as sugarcane and mint, and the remarkable rise of oilseeds, particularly mustard. Such transitions are influenced by market incentives, policy interventions, technological adoption, and socio-economic drivers. The study highlights a double-edged reality—diversification into high-value crops has improved farmer incomes, but it has also intensified concerns over groundwater depletion, ecological imbalance, and nutritional sustainability. The research concludes that long-term resilience requires sustainable land use planning, resource-efficient practices, and balanced crop diversification strategies.

Keywords

Agricultural Land Use, Crop Dynamics, Rice–Wheat System, Cash Crops, Crop Diversification.

Introduction

Agricultural land use reflects the interaction between physical resources, socio-economic forces, and institutional arrangements. Ambedkar Nagar district, located in the eastern plains of Uttar Pradesh, is endowed with fertile alluvial soils, sufficient rainfall, and relatively good irrigation facilities, all of which make it agriculturally productive. However, challenges such as fragmented holdings, over-extraction of groundwater, weak market linkages, climate variability, and poor economic resilience of smallholders continue to hinder sustainable agriculture development.

To ensure efficient agricultural planning, it is vital to analyse where crops are cultivated, how cropping patterns have evolved, and what implications these transformations carry for the district's economy and environment.

Objective of study

1. The first objective of this study is to conduct spatial and temporal analysis of agricultural land use patterns in Ambedkar Nagar district.
2. The second objective is to examine the major factors influencing agricultural land use.
3. The third objective is to evaluate the impacts of agricultural land use changes.

Review of Literature

Studies conducted on agricultural land use in the district reveal that land use has changed according to time and circumstances. Previous research has shown that a part of cultivable land is being converted for non-agricultural activities (such as residential and infrastructural use).

Pandey and Dwivedi (2016), in their research paper, highlighted that traditional agricultural land is gradually decreasing, and diversity and change in cropping patterns can be observed. Due to limited landholdings, small and marginal farmers are primarily engaged in the cultivation of high-yielding staple crops (paddy, wheat), while large and resourceful farmers are cultivating diverse and cash crops.

Jaiswal (2017), in his research on Ambedkar Nagar district, studied the changing patterns of land resource utilization. Findings indicated that increasing population and agricultural intensification have put pressure on land, making environmental management and sustainable use of resources increasingly important.

Satish Chandra (2022) analysed land use changes in Akbarpur tehsil of Ambedkar Nagar district. The study revealed that growing population, urbanization, and increasing pressure on agriculture have altered the traditional land use structure. It was found that excessive pressure on land resources points towards environmental imbalance and unsustainable utilization.

Sharma, Yadav, and Pandey (2023) observed in their research that in some parts of Ambedkar Nagar, a few crops are grown extensively, while in other parts, a mixture of diverse crops is found. This trend has a direct impact on the use of agricultural resources and farmer incomes.

Together, these studies underline the complex interplay between demography, economy, and ecology in shaping land use transitions.

Methodology

The study is largely based on secondary data, drawn from government publications, district statistical handbooks, and online databases. These have been supplemented by field visits, personal observations, and informal discussions with farmers to capture local insights. Data has been analysed through comparative tables, percentage distribution, and trend analysis to trace structural changes over time.

Analysis

Study Area

Ambedkar Nagar district lies between 26°09' N and 26°40' N latitudes and 82°12' E to 83°05' E longitudes, within the eastern Gangetic plain. It experiences a hot sub-humid monsoon climate, characterized by heavy rainfall during the southwest monsoon and occasional winter showers from western disturbances. Average annual rainfall is about 90 cm (KVK Ambedkar Nagar). The 2011 Census recorded a population of nearly 2.4 million, reflecting high demographic pressure on land. Fertile alluvial soils, however, provide a strong foundation for agriculture.

Land Use in Ambedkar Nagar District

Table 01: Land Use in Ambedkar Nagar District (2022–23)

Land Use Category	Area (ha)	% of Total
Total Reported Area	239,475	100.00
Forest Area	328	0.13
Cultivable Waste Land	4,019	1.68
Current Fallow Land	11,060	4.62
Other Fallow Land	7,120	2.97
Barren & Uncultivable Land	3,091	1.29
Non-Agricultural Uses	57,897	24.17
Pasture Land	588	0.25
Orchards/Tree & Shrub Area	2,529	1.06
Net Sown Area	152,843	63.80

Source: Sankhyakiya Patrika Internet Based Data Entry and Retrieval System

Table 01 shows that about 64% of the total reported area is net sown area. Nearly 24% of the land is under non-agricultural use. Forest area is only 0.13%, which is extremely low and adverse for ecological balance. Land under uses other than agriculture is 57,897 hectares (24.17%), reflecting pressure on land from urbanization, roads, buildings, and industrial development. Wasteland and fallow land together constitute 22,199 hectares (9%), indicating that with improved technology and irrigation, cultivable land can be expanded. Pastureland and orchard/forest area are very limited, despite their importance for rural livelihood and ecological balance. In short, though Ambedkar Nagar is primarily an agricultural district, non-agricultural pressure on land is increasing, and forest/pasture areas are very restricted.

Agricultural Land Use Pattern in Ambedkar Nagar District

The agriculture of this district is dominated by food crops. In addition, sugarcane, potato, oilseeds, and pulses are also cultivated over large areas. Among food crops, wheat and rice are predominant.

Table 02: Major Crops in Ambedkar Nagar District (2022–23)

Crop Category	Area (ha)
Paddy	116,373
Wheat	118,413
Barley	953
Maize	712
Millet	999
Total Cereals	237,453
Pigeon Pea	2,698
Lentil	378
Chickpea	1,561
Pea	5,344
Total Pulses	12,423
Total Foodgrains	249,876
Mustard/Rapeseed	12,937
Other Oilseeds	Negligible
Total Oilseeds	12,938
Sugarcane	23,584
Potato	4,849
Other Vegetables	8,097
Tobacco	346

Source: Sankhyakiya Patrika Internet Based Data Entry and Retrieval System

Table 02 shows that the crop-wise land use pattern of Ambedkar Nagar district during 2022–23 reveals a predominantly food grain-oriented agricultural system, with rice (116,373 ha) and wheat (118,413 ha) forming the backbone of a highly established rice–wheat double-cropping structure. Other cereals like barley (953 ha), maize (712 ha), and millet (999 ha) occupy relatively small areas, yet they contribute to dietary diversification and local food security. Pulses cover 12,423 ha where pea (5,344 ha), pigeon pea (2,698 ha), chickpea (1,561 ha) and lentil (378 ha) are the major crops, supporting soil fertility and nutritional intake, though their share remains comparatively low. Mustard/rapeseed is the leading oilseed crop (12,937 ha), while other oilseeds are negligible, indicating limited diversification in this segment. Sugarcane, with 23,584 ha, stands out as the most important cash crop, providing critical income opportunities and raw material for agro-industries. Horticultural crops such as potato (4,849 ha) and other vegetables (8,097 ha) ensure regular market-based earnings for farmers, whereas tobacco (346 ha) remains a minor crop. Overall, with 249,876 ha under food grains—exceeding the net sown area due to multiple cropping practices—the district’s agriculture continues to be dominated by cereals, with gradual but noticeable growth in cash crops and oilseeds to enhance farmers’ income levels.

Agricultural Land Use Trends in Ambedkar Nagar District (1999–2023)

Table 03: Area under Main Crops in Ambedkar Nagar District (ha)

Crop	1999–00	2009–10	2019–20	2022–23
Rice	111,467	114,403	117,536	116,373
Wheat	113,982	118,246	119,654	118,413
Barley	990	829	576	953
Juar	1,460	779	736	999
Bajra	34	16	24	3
Maize	96	714	483	712
Mustard	2,600	3,646	3,942	12,937
Sugarcane	10,672	10,780	10,904	23,584
Potato	4,893	4,178	3,972	4,849
Mint	—	—	—	4,561

Source: Sankhyakiya Patrika Internet Based Data Entry and Retrieval System

It is clear from table no.03 that agricultural land use in Ambedkar Nagar between 1999–00 and 2022–23 shows both stability in staple crops and strong signs of diversification. Rice and wheat have remained the backbone of the farming system, with their area increasing slightly in the 2000s and then more or less stabilising in recent years, which suggests that most of the suitable land for these staples is already under cultivation. In contrast, coarse cereals such as bajra and juar have lost much of their area, indicating that farmers and consumers are moving away from these less remunerative traditional grains.

During the same period, oilseeds, especially mustard, have expanded very rapidly, with the sown area growing almost five times since 1999–00. This reflects

rising market demand and the influence of supportive government schemes, which have made mustard an attractive option compared with many foodgrains. Sugarcane has also spread significantly, with its area more than doubling; this points to strong demand from sugar mills and better income prospects, but it also raises concerns about pressure on water resources because sugarcane is a highly water-consuming crop.

The data also show the appearance and growth of new cash crops. Mint, which was not reported in earlier years, emerged as an important crop by 2022–23, covering more than four thousand hectares and signalling a move toward high-value, possibly export-oriented agriculture. Overall, the pattern suggests that while rice and wheat remain dominant, farmers in Ambedkar Nagar are gradually shifting part of their land from coarse cereals and some traditional crops toward oilseeds, sugarcane, and specialised cash crops in response to changing markets, policies, and income opportunities.

Conclusion

The analysis of agricultural land use in Ambedkar Nagar (1999–2023) reflects both continuity and transformation. Staple crops—rice and wheat—remain the foundation of the district's food system, but the rapid expansion of mustard, sugarcane, and mint highlights a decisive shift toward commercial agriculture. While these changes enhance farmer income, they also pose challenges of water scarcity, soil stress, and reduced dietary diversity.

A sustainable path forward requires balanced crop diversification, investment in water-efficient technologies, and stronger institutional support. Promoting pulses and less water-intensive crops alongside high-value crops can improve income while maintaining ecological balance and nutritional security.

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